

RANKING OF IMAGES BASED ON CAPTION ON SOCIAL MEDIA

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ABSTRACT

Social media applications are being widely popular in this era such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook and etc. The users of social media have been vigorously increasing as that of its data. Hence many researchers started to study and analyse it for different purposes, like based on locations detecting the event photos, clustering its contents, advertising strategies etc. Our Target here is to develop an application for social sites which will arrange images by their captions using TF IDF. Method to rank the keywords of top twenty users based on 10 newly image captions are used. TF-IDF is the method used successfully in this paper to reveal a set of keywords with its ranking. The highest ranking of keywords shows the current topic of user. TF-IDF is an useful to find and rank the keywords of social media users image caption. This application is suitable for Facebook, Instagram etc. for arranging these types of images by caption. We are using Java, JSP as front end and MySQL as backend also will use bootstrap, CSS, JQuery for better GUI. Here we are uploading images and caption then performing TF IDF on that after calculation we are using show result button which will display top 10 images based on our trained caption. This will check all images uploaded by our friends.”

Keywords:

Data mining, Text mining, TFIDF, Social media.

INTRODUCTION

The current era is more popular for social media platforms

Like Facebook, Instagram etc. According to the updated database of Instagram the growth of using Instagram users has been increased. Also Photo uploading by users are increasing day by day. Social media has three types of data i.e text, image, and video. To prove this study text data are used. Text data is the caption and description of the photo uploaded by the user. The keywords based on image caption data are processed and ranking of these keywords is done.

For this Text mining method is used. This is done using TFIDF calculations.

In our project we are using TFIDF method with support vector machine. This Support vector machine algorithm is used for training keywords of captions and Hash map is used for maintain the counts and weights of the keywords. By using TFIDF calculation the ranking keywords are needed in solving classification and clustering tasks as feature extractions. This method is very useful to find and rank the keywords of user's image captions.

In our project the system Admin train the images and add the caption to the particular images, also show the result as per TFIDF calculation. User login to the system application where any user are able to send friend request to other system user. This is for accepting friend request sent by friend. where every user can upload images and add caption on their own account . Here we train the data that are images and their particular captions and calculate TFIDF calculation. As per uploaded data we apply TDIDF calculation. We will get the final top 10 images names which are mostly uploaded. Which will in bar graph format.

Related Work

In 2014, Hu, Manikonda, and Kambhampati [2] wrote that their work is believed to be the first study to conduct a deep analysis of photo content and user activities and types on Instagram. In their study, computer vision and identification by clustering were successfully applied thus eight popular categories of photos and five distinct types of Instagram users were revealed. A dissertation related to Instagram was reported by McCune. He investigated peoples motivations of using Instagram through a survey study of 23 Instagram users [5]. In 2013, Silva, Vaz de Melo, Almeida, Salles, and Loureiro have applied visualization and cultural analytics from various cities on instagram photos in the world to track their cultural and social differences [1].

LITERATURE SURVEY

- [1] T.H.Silva and J.Salles in 2013 suggested that the work of photo sharing system has done by using fundamental tool participatory sensing system (PSSs). For the study of city dynamics the potential of PSSs they have also describe user's behaviours and also observes places which presents application to identify regions of interest in a city based on available data. It also challenges unequal photo sharing frequency both spatially and temporally.
- [2] Manikonda and S. Kambhampati in 2014, stated several insights about Instagram are studied which are: 1) five distinct types of Instagram users in terms of their posted photos, 2) popular photos categories and last one 3) number of followers of user is independent of his/her shared picture on Instagram. Clustering is used to identify different types of users active on Instagram for that they used both quantitative and qualitative analysis.
- [3] Anbarasi M and Buvaneswari in 2014, proposed that an exponential growth in multimedia content in different databases. Access and retrieval of textual and non-textual data has more issues. To resolve this problem information is stored in the cloud environment. In traditional data processing applications complex and large data from internet cannot be stored and processed. Textual retrieval is done through keyword extraction whereas feature extraction technique is done for the image retrieval. K-means algorithm is used to perform clustering. Textual data and non-textual data are retrieved based on ranking.
- [4] Rashika Dandel and Monika Gutal in 2015 stated that Internet is the exponential growth in the multimedia content. Multimedia includes components like texts, images, videos and sounds etc. There are many problems to access and retrieval of both textual and non-textual information so the need to solve this problem by using cloud to store the information in large amount. They used extraction of textual information and non-textual information by using parsing the web page. Textual information is retrieved by keyword extraction whereas image retrieval is done through feature extraction. For performing clustering K-means algorithm is used. By using ranking phase both textual and non-textual information are retrieved together.
- [5] Z. Mccune and J. Thompson in 2011 stated Taking Instagram iPhone app as a source of study, production of social photographic Experienced by users will be examine by this analysis and will ask about the commitment in this always on media network provides.
- [6] C.S. Araujo and D. Silva stated Instagram is a social photo sharing service, in that for the investigation purpose user practices can used. Also people tend to endorse photos with many likes and comments, inducing the rich get richer phenomenon. Findings can support for the future research on sociology and cultural analytics research areas, such as on the proposal of new clustering algorithms based on the user practices in different social media networks.
- [7] A. Kumar and T. M. Sebastian in 2012 stated that With the rise of social networking era there has been a surge of user generated content. People who shares their thoughts on daily basis on blog sites because of its short and simple features. From popular real-time microblogging service, Twitter, where users post real time reactions and opinions about everything with the help of paradigms. To collect a hybrid approach using both corpus based and dictionary based methods to determine the semantic orientation of the opinion words in tweets.
- [8] G. Salton and C. Buckley described SQL as a database language has been widely used in the modern society. They use functions which are based on data processing, it can be used in datamining. Due to the rapid growth of data, large-scale data processing is becoming a focal point of information techniques. Though SQL, can be still be use but where to store the data and how to get the data efficiently, cost effectively, can be a tricky problem. Cloud computing emerges to solve the problem. It is mainly to deal with large-scale data processing. In this paper, they design a data-mining system which can directly deal with SQL processing based on Hadoop, a parallel store and computing platform. Then they will have a discussion about running time's efficiencies.

GOALS & OBJECTIVE

- [1] Arrange images for social sites using Caption for Tf idf calculation.
- [2] The ranking keywords are needed in solving classification and clustering tasks as feature extractions.

- [3] To be improved in terms of understanding slang words and non-English language, adding feature of keywords based on annotation images.

Fig: System Architecture

In this system user will access their account by login in system and upload their photo with caption which will be share with other users. These uploaded photos with caption will train under SVM. This SVM will train the keywords data and captions which will send for further calculation. TFIDF is Term frequency, Inverse document frequency which is used to count the frequent term appear in an document. TF is a process of identifying terms appears in a file or document by given formula:

$$TF(t,d) = \sum_{x \in d} fr(x, t)$$

IDF is a process of identify the number of documents where the terms are present by the following formula:

$$IDF(t) = \log \frac{|D|}{1 + |\{d : t \in d\}|}$$

Where, TF(t,d) function returns the times of terms appear in the document. $|\{d : t \in d\}|$ is the number of documents where terms are present.

The total result is calculated by combining both above TF-IDF equations:

$$TF-IDF(t) = TF(t, d) \times IDF(t)$$

After calculation the weights of keywords are stored in Hash map. These weights are stored temporary in hash map which creates .svm file in which results is stored. This gives us count of ranks.

FUTURE SCOPE

- [1] This is a system the ranking keywords are needed in solving classification and clustering tasks as feature extractions.
- [2] This work still needs to be improved in terms of understanding slang words and non-English language, adding feature of keywords based on annotation images, and so on.
- [3] TF-IDF method is to rank keywords of top 10 maximum followers of Instagram users based on image captions of Instagram.

CONCLUSION

We are using TFIDF method its implemented is very simple and effective in revealing the keywords and its ranking from a certain user. The results show that the highest ranking of keyword is indeed the main topic of a user, indicated by the value of TF-IDF. The higher the TF-IDF value, the more relevant that keyword is to the specific Instagram username. However, this work still needs to be improved in terms of understanding slang

words and non-English language, adding feature of keywords based on annotation images, and so on. Admin train the images and add the caption to the particular images. Also show the result as per TFIDF calculation .

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